

The First Australian Trained Doctors. Patrick Moloney (1843-1904). Part Four: Social Life

Peter Stride

MBBS, MRCP(UK), FRACP, FRCPEdin, FRCP, D. Med - research (UQ);
Senior Lecturer, University of Queensland School of Medicine, Australia

Article History:

Received: 12.11.2024 Revised: 27.11.2024 Accepted: 20.12.2024 Published: 19.02.2025

Abstract

Patrick Moloney, one of the two first graduates of an Australian medical school in 1867, had a most active social life, playing leading roles in many societies. He was a much sought-after speaker. His fluency was enhanced by his literacy, he was fluent in classical Latin and Greek, and widely read in both ancient and modern classical literature. He enjoyed participation in sports and sporting societies though not with much apparent talent!

Keywords: *history, Australian medicine, Patrick Moloney, career.*

Suggested citation: Stride, P. (2025). The First Australian Trained Doctors. Patrick Moloney (1843-1904). Part Four: Social Life. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(2), 28-51. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(2\).03](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(2).03)

The Australian Natives Association

The ANA was an exclusively Australian organisation established in Victoria on 24 April 1871 by a group of young, white Australian-born men. True Australian natives, the first peoples, were not allowed membership, nor women till 1964. As we see with Moloney, non-Australian born white men were also admitted.

It differed from many other societies in that meetings were open to all white males and membership did not involve rituals or regalia. Unlike other societies, it was non-partisan and resolutely non-sectarian, banning the discussion of religious matters.

Dr Moloney's reputation as a speaker was enhanced by his address at a concert given in aid of the benevolent funds of the Victorian Natives' Association, and in doing so certainly did not take the least hopeful view of the prospects of Victoria. He was greeted with laughter and applause especially when citing a drunken

shepherd's description of the colony of Victoria as being bounded by the Commercial Hotel in Echuca and the Bridge Hotel in Flinders Street (The Herald, 1871b; The Argus, 1871; The Riverina Herald, 1871).

Moloney addressed a gathering for the first anniversary of the Australian Natives' Association at the Temperance Hall. He drew a glowing picture of the growth and present prosperity of Australia, and of Victoria particularly, and hoped he would live to see the separation of the colony from the mother country, not a violent and bloody separation such as that which ushered in the independence of America, but like a son going forth with his father's blessing to seek his fortune alone.

He pointed out some of the many advantages this country has to start with, particularly remarking on the salubrity of its climate, and said that Tasmania could show as pretty girls, Victoria as lusty manhood, and Now South Wales as

gentlemanly young men as any in the old country. In the meantime Australia was half a day ahead of England, and he hoped that would be the style of her moral advancement.

The event continued with a concert and a ball (The Age, 1872a; The Age, 1872b).

Moloney, as vice-president of the Australian Natives Association suggested the production of a literary journal, though surprisingly some strong opposition was expressed to the proposition. Moloney commended the Age newspaper for publishing literary offerings (The Age, 1880c).

Dr. Patrick Moloney was nominated as the proposed representative of the Melbourne branch of the Australian Natives' Association at the Colonial and Indian Exhibition to be held in London next year, pending the board of directors obtaining the Premier's approval (The Age, 1885b).

Australian Natives Association Annual Conference wrote to the Chief Secretary requesting that Dr Moloney, a member of the Association, be appointed honorary representative to the Indian and Colonial Exhibition in London (The Herald, 1886).

Dr Moloney presented a paper to the North Melbourne branch of the Australian Natives Association. In the course of a discussion about the republican possibilities for Australia, Dr Moloney compared the suffrage of this Continent with that in England since he spent seven years in the old country, running a profession, and had not a vote during the whole of that time. A man in England had to have two years at a spell in one house and must at least have a room up to a certain amount, otherwise he was not entitled to a vote. This was one reason he loved Victoria more than England, Victoria being more republican (The Herald, 1888b).

Dr Moloney, as a committee member attended the fortnightly meeting of the North Melbourne branch of the Australian Natives Association (The Herald, 1888a).

A proposal was put to the usual fortnightly meeting of the Melbourne branch of the Australian Natives' Association that they should

be the first Australian natives to erect a statue of Peter Lalor, the Australian patriot in Melbourne. Lalor, a native born Irishman was noted for leading the Eureka Stockade rebellion and subsequently becoming speaker in the Victorian Parliament.

Dr. Moloney, who was just newly introduced to the branch, seconded the proposition in a pleasant speech and remarked that a Yankee comrade of Peter Lalor's had told him the speaker that the old Eureka rebel was "a white man, and "one of the whitest men that ever lived." In his opinion, Peter Lalor was as real a Democrat as any man he ever knew (Herald, 1889).

Dr Moloney failed to attend a meeting of the Australian Natives for which the rules demanded a fine. While some members were in favour of remitting the fine, Moloney insisted on paying it as he believed the rules should be enforced. Possibly it was a spirit of generosity that, nevertheless, led the members to remit the fine, notwithstanding the doctor's remarks (The Herald, 1889b).

The Hotham branch of the Australian Natives' Association agreed with Dr Moloney's motion that as many as wished to attend should go to the State Australian Natives' Association Conference (The Herald, 1889b).

Moloney attended the thirteenth annual conference of the Australian Natives' Association (The Age, 1890b).

Dr Moloney attended the anniversary banquet of the Great Western branch of the Australian Natives Association in the local Mechanics' Institute (The Age, 1890c).

Melbourne University

The new University Club had its inaugural dinner at which Moloney gave a humorous and pleasant speech in which he proposed the health of the ladies who were apparently not allowed to be members of this club (The Age, 1873)!

Dr Moloney was elected a committee member at the annual meeting of members of the University Club which then had one hundred and eighty two members (Leader, 1874).

Moloney was elected president at the first annual general meeting of the Melbourne University Association (The Argus, 1879).

A dinner was held in the large hall of the Melbourne Atheneum for eminent gentlemen connected with Melbourne University. Sir Edmond Barry, Chancellor of the University, presided, having on his right his Excellency the Governor, and Sir Bryan O'Loughlen, Professor Strong, Captain Le Patourel and Professor McCoy

The toast to the Ladies was given inevitably by Dr. Moloney though it is not recorded if there were any present (The Age, 1879a).

Dr. Moloney was elected to the committee of management at the first annual general meeting of the Melbourne University Association. Professor Andrew as president congratulated the gentlemen present upon the successful inauguration of the association to bring together the graduates of the Melbourne University for social purposes and for the discussion and promotion of all matters involving the interests and prosperity of the University. About fifty graduates were enrolled as members (The Australasian Sketcher with Pen and Pencil, 1879).

Dr. Moloney, as the vice president, chaired the usual quarterly meeting of the University Association. The principal subject of discussion was the report of the subcommittee upon the better representation of the faculties of law and medicine in the Senate. The report contained a recommendation that bachelors of five years standing should be admitted to the Senate without examination (The Argus, 1879).

Dr P Moloney was elected vice-president at the annual meeting of the Melbourne University Union and also thanked for his contribution to the winter course of lectures which proved a remarkable success (The Argus, 1880d).

Dr Moloney was elected president for the year at the annual general meeting of the Melbourne University Association (The Argus, 1880a).

Dr. Moloney chaired a meeting of the University dinner committee to arrange the annual University dinner. The assistance of Sir

Redmond Barry, Chancellor, and Dr. Brownless, Vice-Chancellor, of the University, and the presence of his Excellency the Governor and the Premier were sought (The Age, 1880a).

Dr. Moloney proposed a toast to Kindred Universities at the annual University dinner, Stating that it was a very pleasant reflection that the sun never sets on the British student (The Age, 1880b).

Dr Moloney, as the president, chaired the ordinary quarterly meeting of the Melbourne University Association (The Argus, 1880).

Dr Moloney and others were expected to address the public inaugural meeting of the University of Melbourne University Union with the vice president, Professor Elkington presiding (The Argus, 1884).

Dr Moloney gave a sardonic but entertaining address at the inaugural meeting of the Melbourne University Union likening the people of Victoria to those of ancient Greece. A second motion, affirming that the union deserved the support of all University men was proposed by the Hon. A. Deakin, seconded by Dr. Moloney, and carried unanimously (Melbourne Punch, 1884c; The Australasian, 1884).

His Excellency the Governor presided over the annual meeting of the Trinity College Dialectic Society attended by a large number of graduates and undergraduates of the University of Melbourne and their friends, among whom were many ladies. Dr Moloney seconded the resolution thanking the speakers who discussed the possibility of Federation and improving the University (The Age, 1885).

Dr. Moloney presided over a lecture entitled 'The Muso in Australia,' in the Wilson Hall of the University in which there were readings of poetry. (The Age, 1885c).

Dr. Moloney attended the annual meeting of the Melbourne University Union (The Argus, 1887; Leader, 1887).

A meeting of University men gathered at the Victoria Coffee Palace to discover the advisability of forming a University Club. Moloney was elected to the initial committee to establish the society and obtain suitable premises

including a sitting room, a dining room and a billiard room (The Argus, 1887).

Dr P Moloney attended the opening smoke night social of the year in connection with the Melbourne Universal Union for an excellent programme of songs, recitations, and instrumental music (The Argus, 1889).

Dr P. Moloney was booked to deliver the second of the Melbourne University Union winter series of lectures, his subject being 'The Delights of Poetry' (The Herald, 1889a).

The Herald noted that the September number of the Melbourne University Review contained an excellent paper by Dr. P. Moloney on the 'Delights of Poetry' (The Herald, 1889d).

Moloney proposed the toast to the University at a smoke concert and social reunion held by members of the Melbourne University Union. Professor Elkington, president, Dr Brownless, Chancellor of the University and about one hundred and fifty members attended. A large number of songs and recitations were given by members (The Age, 1890a).

Moloney was elected vice-president at the annual general meeting of the members of the Melbourne University Union (The Age, 1892).

Dr. Pat Moloney as president, chaired a dinner for the Melbourne University Association. The dinner, which was excellently served by Messrs. Killinger and Goetz at the Vienna Cafe was most enjoyable, and songs and recitations were given by the guests (Melbourne Punch, 1892).

Dr P Moloney was elected one of the vice-presidents at the annual general meeting of the Melbourne University Union (The Argus, 1893).

Sports

Moloney delivered a prologue at the opening of the Opera House amateur dramatic performance in aid of the funds of the University Athletic Club. He was very cordially received and was still more heartily applauded on its conclusion. The Argus printed his speech which is reproduced below as a mark of his literary skills.

PROLOGUE.

*Not such as we, unused to tread the stage
Could hope your kind attention to engage,
But that we move before affectionate eyes,
And speak to hearts too tender to dispense.
How can we fall when such a crowd extend.
Of mothers, sisters, cousins, troops of friends 1
Say, are these ladies? Like flowers that blow
Or truant angels sitting all arow.
Else whence these throbs as if a prison's bird
Charged with a love song granted to be heard;
Vi hence float these odours redolent of heat on
Whence come these eye darts keen as a summer's
loving
We come, unscathed, as Bottom and his crew,
To spend the evening, haply, pleasing you.
Hope not to see Macbeth's or Peter Teazles;
The amateur that was our best has measles;
Another Histrie's failed at his exam,
Our Heavy rather can not move from tram.
Yet though this price occasion both belong
More to go amusing than to stage or Bone;;
Think not all athletes can but do not say,
As dumb as Angles till he saw foul play.
We leave the various, courses, Discifactus,
Cricket and football, rowing, to be actors.
See how the place so wonderfully dense is,
Our treasurer says they're possible [Fancy] these
circenses
One leaves Euclidian parallelepiped,
To strut, not blameless, Uko the Plate biped.
Turley's Diversion unto our were harsh,
We leave walks studious for the Wedding March,
Young Mathematics, just now in eclipse,
Will make no tangent serve with pointing lips.
The young astronomer sees as ladies pass*

Transit of Venus through an opera glass;
Minds not so much the envelope of the sun,
As what encloses her he looks upon.
Young limbs of law shall plaudit dowries taste,
And think this night quite Equitable Waste.
Lands by their loves catch fever quite Quotidian,
Sitting as social as Darwin Ascidian.
Of old the gods changed Boxes, but through prayer
To-night we do it by some Wandering Hair.
Next time we to play, girl graduates may be here.
Soft Caesars to lead captive eye and ear;
it As to whom you dare not whisper Ba!
And learned MLAs not yet M.A.-Ma!
Women shall be as wise, as fit for love :
Was not grave Pallas born from head of Jove?
O times Saturnian! O for Jacob's sun,
To stop the seasons till we saw it done.
Muses and Graces then would live again,
And beaten once more be laddered unto men.
Not knight, but scholarship in peaceful fields
Tile levelled crown scarce rival beauty yields.
New dry ads trip in academic grove,
And nymphs at once slip learning and taste love.
Yet, though we cannot hope to show you bore
Snell classic plays as at Westminster,
We trust in time by scholarly degrees
To boast ourselves the true antipodes.
Remember, bore the day Is earlier born a
Wo book In noontide while 'the English dawn;
Souls, sages say, up Capricornus went,
Let's not realise the earlier hours SO lost.
Friends, let us thank you. What began in (ear
has all the promise of a smooth career;
We go aw hill from study's silent ways,
Hearing the echoes of your kindly praise,

By hill and stream to bear with us away,
Such sweet beginning for a holiday;
Not widest space can o'er your faces hide,
This scene that drops, nut heart from heart divide

The subsequent performance consisted of several popular music pieces (The Argus, 1874; The Argus, 1874a).

At the Sportsman's Coursing Match at Laverton, Mr. Luke Smyley of the Punch carried Dr. Patrick Moloney of the Medical Journal on his back for one hundred yards, easily defeating the Dean of Melbourne, who ran fifty yards. This was no mean feat as Moloney appears a sizeable gentleman (Melbourne Punch, 1877).

A celebration dinner was held in Melbourne for the return of the Australian cricket eleven following the first tour of England. The Australians won twenty one games, drew sixteen and lost only five. This included a win against the MCC at Lords by nine wickets against an English team including W. G .Grace, a game subsequently recognised as a test inspiring a poem in the Punch:

The Australians came down like a wolf on the
fold,
The Marylebone cracks for a trifle were bowled;
Our Grace before dinner was very soon done,
And Grace after dinner did not get a run

Dr. Moloney, in a lengthy and humorous speech as usual, proposed a toast to "The Ladies." as usual, for reasons that have little to do with cricket (The Argus, 1878)!

The non-players of the East Melbourne Cricket Club, including Dr Moloney, proposed a trip to Beechworth to play a cricket match with the non-playing members of the Beechworth Club. A match was arranged on the Beechworth ground on Saturday, 26th January (Ovens and Murray Advertiser, 1879).

Moloney captained a doctors' cricket team playing against the staff of the Melbourne Punch.

The doctors' team won by an innings though Moloney did not figure among the top scoring

batsmen or successful bowlers (The Argus, 1879a; The Argus, 1879b)

Dr Moloney donated a cup to be awarded to the winner of the one mile walking race at the second annual Medical School Athletic Sports. C. Conroy was the successful entrant after a sixty yard handicap. Nearly four hundred students participated in the meeting (The Argus, 1879c; The Herald, 1879a; The Argus, 1879d).

Moloney was one of fifteen from whom a cricket team to represent Melbourne Cricket Club was selected to play a team named E.M.C.C. non-players (The Argus, 1880b).

Dr Moloney proposed a toast to 'Our Native Land' in an eloquent and humorous speech, amongst many other toasts following a spirited hurling match between the Melbourne and Warrnambool Clubs at the Royal Park. (Hurling is an outdoor team game of ancient Gaelic Irish origin) Melbourne won by two goals to one with Moloney participating in the victorious team (The Argus, 1880c).

Dr P Moloney was elected president at the annual meeting of the Pickwick Cricket Club (The Argus, 1884b).

Dr. Moloney played competitive tennis and beat Dr. Mitchell two sets to one (The Australasian, 1885a).

In the second match of the Gold and Silver Racquets tournament, between Mr. O'Shanassy and Dr. Moloney, the doctor was overmatched, but struggled along gallantly, losing three sets to love (The Australasian, 1885b).

Dr. Moloney, newly elected as one of the vice presidents, attended the third annual general meeting of the University Football Club. The code is not specified but prior to rugby league's split from union it was presumably rugby union or football, known as soccer in some Australian circles (The Argus, 1887b).

Dr P Moloney awarded one of the cups awarded to the victors in an extraordinarily successful rowing regatta organised on the Upper Yarra (The Argus, 1889b).

Dr Moloney attended the annual meeting of the Victorian Junior Cricketer' Association at the Albion Hotel (Sportsman, 1889).

Dr. Moloney delivered one of his highly entertaining and instructive lectures on "Recreation" in the Hibernian Hall under the auspices of St. Francis' branch of the Hibernian Society. He strongly recommended dancing and considered cycling was a form of exercise that women could undertake without corsets.

Moloney was not an ardent admirer of football as "The game had," he said, "many attendant brutalities," and he feared it was quite possible to gauge the state of the game from the many injuries caused without actually being an eyewitness of the play. Moloney considered the footballer was predisposed to heart and lung disease from his valvular exertions, and the barracker might get Bright's disease of the kidneys through perching on moist ground (Cobram Courier, 1896; Advocate, 1896).

Moloney joined the debate about the effect and possible benefits on the brain from cycling. One avid cyclist had a brain X-Ray, a new device, through the open mouth revealing multiple dark spots for which Moloney suggested admission for an operation, presumably an exploratory craniotomy and biopsy. Fortunately for the cyclist, this was not taken, or perhaps meant seriously (Melbourne Punch, 1897a).

Moloney attended an Ashes test match at the Oval and along with many Australian spectators, complained bitterly about the cold English 'summer' weather (The Australasian, 1902b).

Moloney participated in many sporting clubs but appeared to prefer the committee to the rugby scrum, facing an audience giving a speech rather than facing the fast bowler at the wicket, poetry to robust tackles!

Catholic Events

Moloney was actively involved with the higher echelons of the Catholic faith in Melbourne, his faith appears an important part of his life.

Dr. Moloney proposed a vote of thanks to Mr. Carty following his discourse on Poetry, Poets and Music in the Atheneum Hall in aid of the St. Vincent de Paul's Orphanage (The Age, 1874).

Dr Moloney proposed a vote of thanks to the Rev Father O Malley on the occasion of his farewell lecture on the Catacombs of Rome. O'Malley was leaving Victoria for the purpose of founding a college of his order in New Zealand. A document was donated to O'Malley thanking him for the great services he had rendered in the cause of religion, science and literature during his sojourn among the Catholics in Melbourne (The Argus, 1878e).

Dr. Moloney was asked to act as the judge for the essay contest to be held by the Melbourne Catholic Young Men's Society (The Advocate, 1879).

Dr. Moloney was booked to deliver an address appropriate to the occasion for the St. Patrick's Day Celebration Grand Concert of national music to be given in the Melbourne Town Hall (Advocate, 1881).

Dr. Moloney and others addressed the half-yearly meeting of the Melbourne Catholic Young Men's Society at the Athenaeum Hall before an excellent musical and elocutionary programme was provided for the entertainment of the visitors (The Australasian, 1881; The Argus, 1882; Illustrated Australian News, 1882).

Dr Moloney was one of several speakers at the half yearly meeting of the Melbourne Catholic Young Men's Society at the Melbourne Athenæum Hall. An excellent musical programme was then provided for the entertainment of the visitors. (The Australian Sketcher with Pen and Pencil, 1882)

Moloney proposed a motion of thanks to Prior Butler for his talk on 'The Thebaid of Egypt, and its Influence on Civilisation' to the Melbourne Catholic Young Men's Society (The Argus, 1882c).

Dr. P. Moloney chaired the weekly meeting of the Victorian Catholic Young Men's Society (The Advocate, 1882).

Dr Moloney, having become an expert on education, gave a lecture on 'Some of the Dangers of Education' to a packed St Patrick's hall. Moloney stated 'it was pitiful to see the systematic manner in which young girls were crammed with useless stores of book learning at

the expense of their physical development he had known many promising young girls pine away and sink into an early grave through this unnatural process of over education.

In the case of the boys many of them by force of perpetual cramming obtained what were known as University honours but on returning to the active life of the world they became arrant failures through their want of business capacity and ignorance of everything except the jargon of the text books It was a great mistake to suppose that education and book knowledge were synonymous and convertible terms.

The best form of education was the knowledge usually acquired by habits of thought and observation and the moral influence of good example. The hours during which children were compelled to study in this colony should be materially reduced It had been authoritatively declared that an adult could not safely indulge in more than three hours continuous intellectual work in a day and yet children were condemned to five hours daily monotonous mental work irrespective of the home lessons which they had to prepare at night

Dr Moloney concluded with a graceful tribute to the Jesuits as the greatest teaching order in the world They had beneficially influenced the educational progress of Europe and it should be more generally known that all the great public schools of England were founded on the scientific system of the Jesuits.

Dr Moloney expressed the opinion amidst considerable applause that the Bible was not a fit book to be placed indiscriminately in the hands of children There were passages in it that no child should peruse just as there were passages in Shakespeare that no child or woman should read. The lecture was interspersed throughout with many amusing anecdotes

A vote of thanks to Dr Moloney was carried by acclamation. A vote unlikely to be repeated today for 'man-speak' (The Argus, 1882d).

Two monster fairs were planned for Easter Monday, also St Patrick's Day in Melbourne.

All true-born Irishmen and faithful sons of St. Patrick were to assemble opposite the Cathedral

at 10 o'clock am for the procession to the Exhibition Building where amongst many performances, Dr. Moloney would present 'Studying Shakespeare intently' (Melbourne Punch, 1883).

Dr. Moloney, now an expert on the colour of stockings, in a health address to the Young Men's Christian Association announced, "I have been shocked and horrified to observe the disfigured appearance that a well-shaped limb has presented from which the covering of a coloured stocking has been removed."

Dr. P. Moloney considered skin would absorb the colour of the stockings and this discolouration would be visible to him as an examining doctor when stockings were removed.

He bitterly regretted the absence of good old white stocking.

The Punch, never one to take anything seriously continued, 'We sincerely trust that the evil is confined to stockings and as Dr. Moloney confined his remarks to these garments, and did not hint, as he might have done, if there had been any occasion for it, of other discolouration, we hope that the worst is known. It would be a terrible thing if these poisonous dyes were being absorbed over a large surface of the body, and we earnestly entreat the Christian young men of Melbourne, to whom the danger is now known, to join with Dr. Moloney and us in warning the girls of Victoria against any further extension of the coloured under garment movement. So long as colour is confined to stockings, we can grapple with it, but let it spread and we cannot tell where the danger will end (Melbourne Punch, 1884a; Melbourne Punch, 1884b)!

Dr. Moloney as president of St. Michael's College, Ballinasloe, received the second most votes in the election for a coadjutor for the Most Rev. Dr. Duggan at a meeting of the parish priests of the diocese of Clontarf (Advocate, 1884).

Moloney was one of a large number of gentlemen, who were mostly ex-students of St. Patrick's College, invited to be presented to his Grace the Archbishop of Melbourne at a meeting of the Sodality of the Blessed Virgin Mary (B.V.M.)

Dr Moloney was appointed a member of a subcommittee from a gathering of about forty graduate and under-graduate Catholic members of the University, to make arrangements for the presentation of an address to the Archbishop of Melbourne, conveying their welcome to his Grace (Advocate, 1887a).

Dr. Moloney and others joined a discussion on the paper on "Sleep and Dreams" read by Dr O'Sullivan at a well-attended meeting of the Sodality of the B.V.M. (Advocate, 1887b).

The Riverview Jesuit College in Sydney having been just completed, at a recent meeting of the building fund committee of the college it was resolved that all fresh subscriptions received from that date to the opening of the new college should be formed into a fund to be known as the "Dalton Testimonial Fund." Father S J Dalton was the first Irish Jesuit missionary to Australia in 1866 and was responsible for the development of a number of churches and educational institutions. He oversaw the transfer of St Patrick's College, East Melbourne to the Jesuits and inspired the construction of the Riverview Jesuit College.

Dr. Moloney, of Melbourne, in speaking to the resolution, paid an eloquent tribute to the educational achievements of the Jesuits, and bore personal testimony to the high and general esteem in which Fr. Dalton was held in Victoria, In the words of Tennyson, " His life was like a line of light." He could not but congratulate the Jesuit Fathers and their friends on the magnificent pile now crowning the Riverview heights (Advocate, 1889).

Dr Moloney attended the annual retreat of the members of the Sodality of the Blessed Virgin attached to St. Patrick's College, and inevitably was one of those delivering a speech (Advocate, 1890).

Moloney attended a meeting in St. Patrick's Cathedral, under the presidency of his Grace Archbishop Carr, for the purpose of raising funds for the completion of the cathedral, as an appropriate memorial to the late Dean Fitzpatrick.

Dr. P. Moloney seconded a resolution, which was carried unanimously: "That it is due to the

memory of Dr. Fitzpatrick that his name should be perpetuated by the people of Victoria, and that the most suitable monument should be the completion of St Patrick's Cathedral" (Weekly Times, 1890).

Dr. Moloney seconded the vote of thanks to Rev. Isaac Moore, for conducting a retreat for the Sodality of the B.V.M., St Patrick's College. in a short and impressive speech (The Advocate, 1891c).

Dr. P. Moloney appeared before a fairly large audience in the Sodality Hall of St. Patrick's College to read a paper entitled "The Science of Bathing." His talk rich with illustrations culled from classical literature, spoke of the interest with which he always heard news from the sea. He mentioned the feat of Dalton, the American, who swam across the English Channel from Boulogne to Folkestone, a distance of twenty miles, in twenty-three hours, notwithstanding that he had to battle with two flood tides whilst the temperature of the water was sometimes as low as 45 Fahrenheit. The swimmer found it to his advantage to rest on his back, and Moloney remembered that Miss Lacy, who was rescued after a long immersion in the water when the Quetta was lost, survived by lying on her back.

Moloney stated that children swim easily and in Fiji the swimming lessons are imparted at such an early age that the natives are unable to remember the period at which they were unable to swim. He noted in Colombo Harbour that the natives are wonderfully expert in diving

Referring to the important subject of the restoration of the apparently drowned, the lecturer said he did not think that the attempts to restore animation should be given up at the end of twenty minutes, and he would continue these efforts for a couple of hours. There was, he pointed out, a difference of opinion among medical circles as to the best method of restoring animation, for whilst some doctors favoured the method of raising and depressing the arms, others expressed the opinion that the rolling from side to side motion is the best.

Moloney considered that no part of the world is better adapted for swimming or less taken advantage of for the purpose than Victoria.

Presumably, he had not been to Queensland (The Herald, 1891; Advocate, 1891b).

Dr. Moloney seconded the vote of thanks to his Grace the Archbishop of Melbourne for his talk on the Irish Catholics of Australia (Advocate, 1891a).

A successful meeting was held in St Francis' Church, Lonsdale Street, for the purpose of devising means to provide for the restoration and renovation of the church. Dr Moloney moved a motion stating, " That immediate steps be taken for the renovation of St Francis' Church." This seemed a pointless motion beyond giving Moloney a soapbox as that was the purpose of the meeting (The Argus, 1891a).

Dr Moloney joined a committee to organise the reception for the visit of Cardinal Moran and the Australian Catholic Hierarchy on their arrival in Melbourne (Advocate, 1891d)

Dr. P. Moloney, described as 'the well-known and popular medico,' opened a Cake and Novelty Fair in St. George's Catholic Hall, fundraising to pay off a debt that has been accumulating on the schools of the parish (The Herald, 1892a; Advocate, 1892).

Dr Moloney was one of the eminent citizens of Melbourne invited to attend the annual distribution of prizes at St. Francis Xavier's College, Kew, by his Excellency the Governor.

Moloney also attended a concert at the Melbourne Town Hall to raise funds for the Sisters of Charity (Advocate, 1893b).

Mr. E. O. McDevitt gave a lecture entitled "Incidents in the Life of Frederick Ferdinand Count Von Beust. a European Diplomatist" before the Sodality of the B.V.M., in the lecture hall of St. Patrick's College. (A diplomatist emphasizes an individual's expertise in the study and theory of diplomacy. Diplomats are often scholars, writers, or researchers who provide advice and guidance on foreign policy through research and analysis of international relations, a more intellectual person than the average politician diplomat).

Dr. P. Moloney proposed a vote of thanks to Mr. McDevitt for his very able and interesting lecture (The Argus, 1893a; Advocate, 1893a).

Dr. P. Moloney delivered a lecture at the first meeting for the year of the Sodality B. V. M. Society at the Sodality Hall on the physiology of football. Moloney dealt with his subject in a most humorous and characteristically entertaining manner and was extremely instructive. He referred to the antiquity of the game of football which was played by the Greeks and Romans. He spoke of Rugby Union, probably the only football he played attending a private boys school, and, evoking controversy, considered the Irish physique was the optimal for football (The Age, 1894a; The Herald, 1894a).

The Most Rev. Dr. Carr, Archbishop of Melbourne delivered an address on Irish Melodies in St. Patrick's School Hall for the benefit of St. Patrick's Cathedral Building Fund. The address was illustrated by the performance of a number of the best known and most admired of Thomas Moore's Irish melodies. Dr. P. Moloney proposed A vote of thanks to the Archbishop for his address (The Age, 1894a).

A great fair in aid of St. Patrick's Cathedral Building Fund was opened by His Excellency the Governor. Dr Moloney had written an ode either to be sung or read during the event.

I.

*Tread ye with reverent feet
In this high Fane, where meet
We, Pilgrims from our birth.
Bend the adoring knee,
For here is Sanctuary,
A minor Heaven on earth.*

11.

*Here pause all worldly aims,
Ambition's loud acclaims
Sink into silence here,
Or change to Canticle,
That form each chapel cell
In antiphon sounds clear.*

III.

*'Neath spandrel, shaft and aisle
We have no thought for guile,
No room for sigh or wail;
But such an acolyte,
With heart in lustral white,
Our inmost thoughts unveil.*

IV.

*Vow by this Patron Saint
No sin shall e'er attain,
Aa ne'er did his, thy soul.
Make, like these spires that climb,
Tho effort all sublime
To reach the heavenly goal.*

V.

*These altars shall make cease
To Rosaries of Peace
All evil thoughts and deeds.
Man's Brotherhood to man
In the first Church began,
And on in this succeeds.*

VI.

*Join with our Hierophant
In echoing hymn and chant
Before the Holy Rood.
Let Litany and Psalm
Break through the brooding calm,
And tell our gratitude.*

VII.

*Behold ! this lofty Dome
Is built, through God, a Home*

*For youth, for age, for all.
Come ye who sorrow hither,
And lift your voices whither
Shall showers of mercy fall.*

VIII.

*By jasper portals wait
Angels in princely state
On battlements empearled,
To welcome to the Throne
The low who here unknown
The banner-cross unfurled.*

IX.

*That other Temple where
Nor grief, nor cark nor care,
Nor any sound of moan,
Disturbs the sapphire air,
But seraph's harpings rare
Across the stars are blown* (Weekly Times, 1894a; The Herald, 1894b).

Dr. P. Moloney was noted as vice-president when the office holders of the St Patrick's Cathedral Building Committee were recorded for the annual Fair (Table Talk, 1894).

Moloney was one of the many guests attending the reception given by the Archbishop of Melbourne in celebration of the opening of St. Patrick's Cathedral (Advocate, 1897).

Other Events

Moloney was elected a new member of the horticultural society.

Dr Moloney responded particularly eloquently for the ladies following the toast to the Ladies at the annual dinner of the Medical Society. About thirty members were present besides the visiting guests. The evening was spent in that exceedingly pleasant manner which distinguishes these annual gatherings of the society according to the press (The Age, 1870)

A banquet was held in the Williamstown Oddfellows' hall for Mr. Jeremiah Dwyer, one of the defeated candidates for Williamstown, and Dr. Moloney was amongst sixty eminent guests (The Herald, 1871a)

St. Patrick's Day was this year celebrated by a grand ball and supper at St Patrick's Hall. Unsurprisingly Dr. Moloney was present and proposed a toast to St. Patrick's Society and the day we celebrate (The Argus, 1872a).

Moloney and other doctors addressed the Foot and Mouth Disease Commission commending the efficacy of disinfectants for the destruction of germs of the disease (Geelong Advertiser, 1872).

Dr Moloney gave an address on the benefits of elocution to an evening of entertainment organised by Hill at the Temperance Hall for a number of his former pupils (The Australasian, 1872a).

Moloney arrived at the much anticipated Mayor's Fancy Dress Ball dressed as the Earl of Surrey, according to the Argus in a handsome dress, consisting of blue velvet doublet puffed with maroon satin edged with white fur, and with gold trimmings, and gold trimmed belt ; scarlet velvet robe trimmed with gold and with white fur blue tower cap trimmed with fur, low shoes, buckles and rosettes (The Argus, 1874).

Dr. Moloney made a humorous and characteristic speech in responding on behalf of the ladies at a banquet held for Mr. Ellery, the Government Astronomer. His Excellency the Acting-Governor and many distinguished Victorians attended. Professor Halford, MD, FRCP, of Melbourne University was in the chair (The Age, 1875).

Moloney was elected an ordinary member of the Royal Society of Victoria (The Argus, 1877).

Dr. Moloney contributed an essay on the suicidal stage of existence to The Melbourne Review with a view to prove that every individual man, before arriving at maturity, passes through a painful intellectual phase, which may positively be called suicidal and that its manifestations are feeble among "the general," but well-marked among those of average intelligence, and of startling

proportions among those gifted with genius or ability.

Much of the newspaper is related to illustrate his erudition, his widespread reading of great authors, and to reveal why one journalist describes him as one of our great literati.

Dr. Moloney argued that nations as well as individuals go through the suicidal stage, and that there was an epoch in the histories of both Greece and Rome, in which "suicide became not only a contemplated, but an actual terminus for the unsatisfied longings of the intellect." In modern Europe, this morbid tendency began to manifest itself, he considers, with Werther, and has lasted with somewhat lessening intensity till now. This was written in 1877 and sadly applies more in 2024.

So intense and general, ' he says, " was the early attack, that it not only coloured the thought, but profoundly affected the actions of the era, Goethe, Chateaubriand, Lamartine, and even George Sand, deliberately attempted suicide, and among the followers of Goethe with his Scepticism, Nihilism, and contemplation of Suicide, we find such notable names as Byron, Alfred de Musset, Leopard, Espronceda Ugo Foscolo, Heine, Pushkin, Lenau, Petofi. To them the world is but grief and illusion. They all suffered keenly the ' Weltschmerz ' (world pain), of which Scho perhaps is the philosopher To Lamartine the whole universe shouted ' Die,' and 'the prophetic soul of the wide world, dreaming of things to come,' saw in suicide the only terminus and even for life " (Melbourne Review, 1877).

Dr. Moloney contributed an article to Mr. Garnet Walch's Christmas annual for 1877, entitled Hash, placing Moloney in company with writers such as Marcus Clarke (The Age, 1877).

Dr Moloney authored an article for the St Patrick's college gazette, though no details are given (The Herald, 1877).

Dr. Moloney and three other gentlemen were selected as a committee of inspection observing Professor Baldwin giving a demonstration of Spiritualism and magic tricks. The committee were duly bewildered until Baldwin explained the sleight of hand, though Moloney may have been

concerned by Balwin's first trick, the transmutation of wine into water (The Age, 1878b).

Dr P Moloney delivered his lecture entitled "A day with my liver" at the Carlton Hall, being the fourth of a series of Health Lectures arranged by the Australian Health Society. The lecture was listened to with marked attention by a crowded audience. One trusts he recalled his comments about Claret and Brandy in his lecture of four months previously (The Argus, 1878c).

Dr. Moloney presided at a gathering in the Town Hall where the Rev. M. Watson gave a lecture on Catholic Tyrol and particularly on the deeds of Holer, the patriot (Age, 1878).

Dr. Moloney was the vice-chairman at a farewell dinner for Mr. David Jones at the Union Club Hotel prior to Jones leaving Victoria for a lengthy stay in the old country (The Australasian, 1878).

Dr P Moloney was nominated to become a committee member at the annual meeting of the members of the Melbourne Athenaeum. He received the second highest vote duly being elected (The Argus, 1879c; The Argus, 1879d).

Dr. Moloney attended the usual monthly meeting of the committee of the Melbourne Athenaeum following financial statements the election of a new secretary occurred. Moloney seconded the motion to have a series of ballots eliminating the candidate with the lowest vote each time. J. H. B. Curtis was duly elected (The Age, 1879b).

Dr Moloney was a contributor to a literary work just published by Mr. George Robertson titled Easter Omelette. Mr. A. P. Martin, The editor of the Melbourne Review supplied three articles to the 'Omelette' (The Riverina Herald, 1879).

Moloney as a committee member attended a special meeting of the committee of the Melbourne Atheneum which considered the purported appointment of the secretary was illegal, irregular, and consequently invalid, by reason of the election not having been conducted in accordance with the rules of the institution. Amid much animosity it was agreed there would be a new election for secretary next

meeting. Moloney thought either candidate was competent (The Argus, 1879e).

Dr Moloney donated a guinea to the Kickham Testimonial Fund. Charles Kickham was an Irish author and patriot who once had an ambition to become a doctor (Advocate, 1879).

A large celebration took place in Melbourne to commemorate the centenary of the birth of Thomas Moore, the famous Irish poet. Some of his musical compositions were played and 'The Minstrel Boy' sung. Dr Moloney seconded a vote of thanks to Sir Bryan O'Loughlen for chairing the most convivial gathering. O'Loughlen, born in Dublin had an eminent career in law and politics and like Moore was a staunch Irish nationalist and Catholic (The Herald, 1879b; The Argus, 1879f).

Dr Moloney was re-elected as a committee member for the year at the ordinary monthly meeting of the Royal Society.

Dr Moloney and other doctors agreed to deliver free public medical lectures at the Social Science Congress and subsequently in the courses of free public health lectures in Richmond (The Argus, 1879g).

Dr Moloney was elected a member of council of the Australian Health Society (The Argus, 1880d).

Dr Moloney attended the funeral of the celebrated artist, Mr. Thomas Wright (The Herald, 1881a).

According to 'The Gallery,' Dr Moloney stated that the excessive use of tea by shepherds and bushmen accounted for the frequency of insanity among them (The Herald, 1881b).

The Ballarat paper reported that Dr Moloney authored a clever article entitled, 'The Suicidal Stage of Existence.' He generalised that the majority of persons about the age of thirty had grave and unpleasant promptings to terminate a life which was to them dull, stale, flat, and unprofitable. Arguing from the experiences of Goethe, Shakespeare, Schiller, and Hugo, he elaborated a series of ingenious suppositions, which made more than the ordinary talk in Melbourne society.

This followed the death of a wretched man who hung himself in the Treasury Gardens with some wild show of justice on his side. "My health is gone," he wrote, "and my money is gone, so I must try the next state; this has become too hard" (Ballarat Star, 1881).

A song written by Dr Moloney was sung by Miss Rosina Carandini at 'Ye Olde Englishe Fayre' opened by the Bishop of Melbourne, in the presence of his Excellency the Governor and the Marchioness of Normanby. Arrangements had been made with two prominent citizens attired in the original costume of Beef Eaters to function as yeomen of the guard to his Excellency, One hundred and fifty ladies were dressed in period costumes embracing the period between Queen Elizabeth and King George IV (The Age, 1881).

The members of the Atheneum Club entertained Judge M Farland at a dinner to congratulate him on his recent elevation to the bench.

Moloney proposed "The Bar." He regretted that the profession of medicine had hitherto not made its mark in the history of the colony as the legal profession had done, but he believed that in time it would take the position to which it was entitled as an honourable and learned profession (The Argus, 1882a)

The Punch published a derisive sarcastic article claiming a deputation of doctors including Moloney had visited Mr. Bent, the Minister of Railways to thank him for the amount of first-class work he had recently thrown in their way following several train crashes. They thanked him for his public spirit and his forethought and kindness in supplying them, the medical men, with a continuous supply of good cases.

Dr. Moloney, apparently called upon to give an address, stated that he felt honoured by being called upon to do so and that he had always admired the Commissioner's slap-dash style of doing things. Moloney hoped Bent would continue to work the collision department with the same efficiency as heretofore.

The Commissioner, in reply, said, according to Punch, that he was more than delighted to receive the address just read and should keep it as an heirloom in his family (Melbourne Punch, 1882).

Moloney was in the paper again expressing his opinion on the correct preparation and benefits of a cup of tea. Water well oxygenated as from a flowing mountain stream should be boiled once at 212 deg. F. and the tea infused for not more than three minutes so the tannin has not time get dissolved out. It should then be drunk, not more than half-a-pint at a time, at breakfast (Herald, 1883).

Dr. Moloney, as the secretary, supervised the postponed art-union drawings exhibition and the awarding of prizes. Mrs. P. Moloney won a prize for a much-admired silk patch-work quilt (Advocate, 1883).

A Victoria Shakspearian show book published in London arrived in Melbourne containing amongst other writings by Victorians, some poems and a spring madrigal by Moloney (The Argus, 1884a).

Moloney was one of hundreds of distinguished guests invited to a Levee held at Government House by His Excellency the Governor to commemorate the Queen's birthday (The Argus, 1885).

Dr Moloney attended the public meeting held in the Town Hall under the presidency of His Excellency the Governor, to promote the movement for the erection of a statue in Melbourne of the late General Gordon who had been killed in the siege of Khartoum in January (The Argus, 1885b).

A public meeting of the citizens of Melbourne who desired to maintain the integrity of the empire, and to bring its parts into closer union and co-operation with federation of the Australian States was held with a large enthusiastic crowd of men and women.

A resolution, moved by Professor Elkington, and seconded by Dr. Moloney declared, "That such society be now formed under the rules of the Imperial Federation League, to be called 'The Victorian Branch of the Imperial Federation League' (Bendigo Advertiser, 1885a; 1885b).

Dr P Moloney and his wife and daughter were reported to be travelling overland to Sydney. The article did not clarify whether this was by train or coach (The Argus, 1885a).

The Albion held their third annual meeting at the Albion Hotel and appointed office bearers for the following year. Dr Moloney was elected treasurer. The nature of this society is not apparent beyond just being a hotel social gathering (Sportsman, 1885).

Mrs. P Moloney gave an "At Home" at her residence last Monday evening. About eighty guests were present. The arrangements for the comfort of the guests were very complete, and a very enjoyable evening was spent. A large home with expensive catering is implied (Table Talk, 1885b).

Dr. Moloney spoke with other speakers to the Shakespeare Society, his topic being 'Philosophy in the Tempest' (Table Talk, 1885a).

Dr. Moloney distributed the prizes at the St. George's School annual exhibition, concert, and distribution of prizes.

Moloney said that everything he had seen and heard that evening had given him immense pleasure, but he derived most enjoyment from handing to each child the well-earned reward to which they had become entitled. A large and valuable collection of books and medals had been distributed. Dr. Moloney, as he gave each book, made some complimentary remarks on the talent and perseverance of the prize winner (Advocate, 1886).

Dr Moloney embarked on P and O's RMS *Bengal* commencing his voyage to England (The Herald, 1886).

Dr Moloney attended the opening of the Colonial and Indian Exhibition in London by Her Majesty the Queen. The Colonial and Indian Exhibition of 1886 was held in South Kensington in London with the objective to (in the words of the then Prince of Wales) "stimulate commerce and strengthen the bonds of union now existing in every portion of Her Majesty's Empire (The Argus, 1886a).

The Punch listed eleven distinguished Australians currently residing in England including Dr Moloney as the 'Australian Eleven' (Melbourne Punch, 1886).

Dr Moloney and his family arrived back in Melbourne aboard the R.M.S.S. Valletta (The Argus, 1887).

Dr Moloney and many other eminent citizens attended an exhibition in the Athenaeum promoting "The Picturesque Atlas of Australia" edited by Andrew Garran. Dr. Moloney replied to a toast to Literature and Art (The Herald, 1887b; Leader, 1887).

Every visitor will agree, wrote The Herald, that the feature of the Artists smoke night soiree was Dr Moloney's address, which broke up fresh ground, the emotions of a Victorian on his first view of the glories of Europe in pictures. He aptly spoke of the Renaissance, when all the arts went hand in hand, with their development for such was ever the rule from the age of Pericles, and the ancients figured the Muses as all akin.

The London streets were to him living pictures, and he saw those effects which the Frenchman Nittis so admirably hit off. (Giuseppe De Nittis (February 25, 1846 – August 21, 1884) was one of the most important Italian painters of the 19th century). The Doctor put in an eloquent touch about the streets of Florence, showing that he had a rich portfolio of Reminiscences, a Liber Studiorum which ought to be further drawn upon. Gracefully did he allude to the Pictures of Travel written by his accomplished friend J. S., who was present; and J. S. obliged with a reading from Mrs Caudle, where Job has been visiting the Skylark Artistic Club, which Jerrold seemed to have written with a sly prophetic reference to the Victorian Artists' Smoke Night.

Dr. Moloney impressed the Herald when he referred to an eloquent passage in Renan, to the effect that while it was grand to contemplate a land with a magnificent past it was still more inspiring to consider the land with a magnificent future. So, he returned well contented to blooming Victoria, rushing and bounding in the path of prosperity. Seldom one hears an off-hand impromptu little speech so clever as this of Dr. Moloney's, as good as a page out of a first-class book (The Herald, 1887a).

The alumni of St. Patrick's College proposed their annual dinner. Speeches by Dr. Moloney,

the chairman, and others were planned (The Age, 1887).

Dr Moloney was one of two hundred and sixty guests attending a banquet to honour Mr. Deakin, at the Atheneum.

Mr. Deakin delivered a splendidly-delivered, exhaustive, and eloquent speech, lasting thirty minutes, the chief points of which were as follows:—Gentlemen in London in prominent positions had asked him how he could be content to remain in the colonies, he replied he was belonging to his own country. The conference had caused a great change in the policy of the mother country towards the colonies, not only with regard to England's international policy, but her foreign relations.

We had been endowed with a great heritage in the land, which was the source of all wealth, and in the privilege of self-government and through the conference had obtained an opportunity of dealing with Imperial Ministers face to face, instead of through a veil of permanent officials who did not discriminate freely between Crown and independently governed colonies.

One of the greatest effects of the conference was that it had placed officials in Downing street in their proper position. Hitherto we had not been a truly independent body; we had shown ourselves ready to exercise the powers of a self-governing state, able to protect our commerce on the ocean. The position of the colonies had been summed up by the Right Hon. W. E. Forster as either separation or federation, but he declined to accept that. The idea of separation had to come from the mother country, not from the colonies; but we could not but feel if Victoria would be but a petty State, totally unable to defend itself. Even Australasia would at the present time be but a feeble power without the mother country behind it; finding a difficulty in defending even its own territory without foreign influence or power to exercise its policy in relation to the Pacific proposals, for separation meant all loss and no gain, but we are not prepared to fall into the arms of the Federation league; for Federation meant loss to the principle of self-Government; the bands that bound us to the motherland were those of kindred, race, and language. The improvements in steam navigation

were bringing us face to face with a graver danger, the competition of other countries, such as Mexico, which, with like climatic conditions to ours, were taking advantage of duties and bounties to compete with us.

The first object of Australians should be the federation of Australia. How could we complain of the indifference of the mother country when we were not able to come to an arrangement with a colony within a stone's throw of us? It was to bodies like the Australian Natives, which, without political objects or party' organisation, arrived at the cultivation of a national spirit, that we look for the policy of the future.

Chief Justice Higinbotham, on rising to propose "Australia and Australian Federation," received a perfect ovation, all present rising, waving their handkerchiefs, and giving loud cheers. He admitted that he was an Irishman by birth, but many of the pioneers claim to be older colonists than those who succeeded them, into whose hands the destiny of the colony was fast passing. Sir Henry Forster, in a little book in which light was let in upon the dealings of the Colonial Office, had admitted that ninety-nine out of every hundred despatches relating to the colonies were never seen by the Secretary of State. The events recently taken place would bring about co-operation or federation, but unless the Government took care the advantage gained would slip from them.

Mr. G. H. Wise, mayor of Sale, also responded. Dr Moloney, in a most eloquent address, proposed "The Pioneers of Australia," to which Mr. Chas. Brown responded.

The speaking throughout the evening was, however, far above the average of ordinary banquets, and the receptions given to Mr. Deakin, the Speaker, and Mr. Justice Higinbotham were perfect ovations, the proceedings throughout being exceptionally good (The Ballarat Star, 1887).

Moloney and Mrs. Moloney arrived at Hobson's Bay aboard the R.M S. Oroya from Sydney (The Argus, 1887b).

Dr Moloney was reported amongst the arrivals aboard the T. S. N. Southern Cross from Hobart (The Argus, 1887c).

Dr Moloney was one of many eminent guests at the Australian Club Ball (Punch, 1887).

Members of the medical profession met to tender a farewell dinner to Dr W. Cutts on the occasion of his departure for Europe. The chairman, Dr Neild, in proposing the toast of the guest of the evening, dwelt upon the humble and honourable manner in which Dr Cutts had held his place for thirty years as a leading member of the medical profession in Victoria,

Amongst several toasts for the night, Dr Moloney proposed the Medical School of the University (The Argus, 1888).

Dr. Moloney proposed a motion to the provisional committee for the next session of the Intercolonial Medical Congress of Australasia, that the congress should assemble on Monday, January 7th, 1889, and should rise on Saturday, January 12th. The large and representative attendance agreed unanimously (The Argus, 1888b).

The annual dinner of the "old boys" of St. Patrick's College was held in the upper hall of the college. Theology, medicine, law, literature, art and science were well represented in the persons of former students, though medical men would have been found to be in the majority.

Dr. Moloney proposed a toast to "Our Old Masters," coupled with the name of his Grace the Archbishop, Rev. W. Kelly, to whose energy, wit, and scholarship he paid a splendid tribute (Advocate, 1888).

Dr. Moloney claimed that new-born colonial infants average one pound heavier than those who came to life in England (Melbourne Punch, 1888a).

Dr. Moloney presented some Special Prizes, the results of the various educational and other competitions at the juvenile industrial exhibition (The Australasian, 1888).

Dr Moloney addressed the fourth annual meeting of the Victorian Women's Suffrage Society.

He referred at some length to the position women had held and proved themselves capable of holding. He was a member of the society

because he behoved it was right to belong to it. In women not being admitted to the bar he drew attention to the fact that Shakespeare, when he framed the part of Portia, considered that women possessed the abilities to undertake the place.

In his own profession there were eighteen ladies practicing in London with the greatest success, and in the examination one of them had taken honours above any of the men. In all branches there were celebrities among the women, and at present four who were on the stage drew far higher receipts than any ten men.

Subsequently a meeting was held at Dr Moloney's residence, West Melbourne, to officially announce the formation of a society to be known as the Women's Australian Suffrage Society. The rules of the Victorian Women's suffrage society were adopted and among the appointed office bearers for the year, Moloney was elected treasurer (The Herald, 1888c; The Herald, 1888d).

A volume entitled a century of Australian Song was published in London, nicely printed and elegantly bound. One of Dr Moloney's songs of yesteryear was included entitled "Queen City of the Golden South" says that she was "a witness when I kissed the mouth of her whose eyes out-blazed the starry fires."

The Punch noticed with a blush that Dr. Moloney informed us that he has grown a good deal older and steadier since he wrote this, and we think it rather a shame that it should be brought up in judgment against him now (Melbourne Punch, 1888b).

The Punch commented upon St. Patrick's College claims amongst its old boys are Melbourne's most conspicuous "doctors," both of laws and medicine. Dr. Madden is unquestionably the one bright particular star of the legal firmament, and Dr. Moloney is as brilliant in medicine, although, unlike Dr. Madden, he has some competitors.

The Punch believed neither of the doctors were actually natives, though they are next door to it. In love and sympathy they are more Australian than the natives, and are illustrations that the

hard and fast rule of the A.N.A. is one that ought to be abolished (Melbourne Punch, 1889a).

Dr P. Moloney attended a meeting on the Victorian Artists Society (Table Talk, 1889b).

A largely attended public meeting was held on Monday night in the Melbourne Town Hall, to support the concept of a Sunday newspaper. A letter was received from Dr Moloney, and many others expressing sympathy with the desire to open a Sunday paper and also to open museums, public libraries and art galleries on Sundays (Mount Alexander Mail, 1889).

Dr. Moloney hosted a dinner attended by the leading doctors in Melbourne to commemorate the career of Dr. F. T. West Ford, who came to Victoria in 1849 and is shortly to leave for the old country. No member of the medical profession has occupied a more notable position than he, both generally as a practitioner having a large practice among the older colonists, and as an official holding important public appointments (Table Talk, 1889d).

Dr. Moloney chaired an artistic evening meeting in which poems and songs were presented. Punch considered that wealth and power may not have been represented but intellect, taste, genius and virtue were greatly on display (Melbourne Punch, 1889d).

Dr. P. Moloney and Mrs. P. Moloney attended the Fancy Dress Ball given by Sir William and Lady Clarke at Cliveden, Moloney wearing academical dress and Mrs. Moloney looked well as Lady Jane Grey (Melbourne Punch, 1889c; Table Talk, 1889c).

He considers the difference between Tweedledum and Tweedledee may be very considerable in the medical profession. Dr. Moloney wrote to the papers to explain that it is not he, but Dr Maloney, the member of Parliament who has immortalized himself over the Lady Loch diamonds. Dr. P Moloney draws attention to the difference between O and A and hence his public a-vowel (Melbourne Punch, 1889c)!

Dr Moloney was one of several hundred invited guests at His Excellency the Governor, the Earl of Hopetoun's first levée (The Argus, 1889a).

The Centennial Magazine, due to be published in the new year will contain a descriptive paper on the Melbourne Hospital with illustrations of the Hospital buildings and a portrait of Drs. Moloney (Table Talk, 1889a)

Dr. Moloney's brother, Mr. Michael Moloney, for many years inspector of telegraph for the Northern district, died at Newcastle (The Herald, 1890).

Dr Moloney attended the first water-colour exhibition of the Victorian Artists' Society at Buxton's Gallery, Swanston Street, Melbourne and purchased 'A Celestial Sketch' by Mr., Matlier for three guineas (Table Talk, 1890).

Moloney was one of some thousand gentleman invited to a Levee to celebrate the anniversary of Her Majesty's Birthday holiday (The Argus, 1891).

Dr. P. Moloney thanked His Excellency the Governor for attending Dr. W. H. Embling's lecture "Reminiscences of the English Brigade in Garibaldi's Campaign" at the Medical Students' Society meeting (The Argus, 1891b).

Moloney attended the Victorian Sketching Club's second exhibition of paintings and sketches at Merrilee's Art Hall (Melbourne Punch, 1891).

Moloney was one of a fashionable gathering attended the private view of the Anglo-Australian collection of pictures which was opened last week at the Exhibition Building (Leader, 1892).

The Herald described Moloney as the 'cultured and gentlemanly' Dr P. Moloney when he and others gave speeches to farewell Mr. Jeremiah Boland at a sumptuous banquet prior to his departure for a visit to the Old World aboard the *S S Oceana* (The Herald, 1892b).

Dr and Mrs. P Moloney amongst many others attended Lady Hopetoun's at home ball (The Australasian, 1892a).

P, Moloney holidayed at Noumea, including a visit to the convict settlement on Isle Novi. He wrote at length to a friend about the Simian appearance and tattoos of one of the convicts, and this man's likeness to William alias Deeming,

a recent malefactor in Melbourne (The Australasian, 1892b).

Dr. P Moloney was elected a member of the Old Colonists Association at the monthly meeting (The Argus, 1892a).

Moloney attended the fund-raising St. Vincent's Hospital Ball with the State Governor and other leading citizens of Melbourne (Melbourne Punch, 1893).

Mr. D. J. O'Donoghue's "Biographical Dictionary of the Poets of Ireland, part three" had just been issued embracing all the contributors to the rich stores of Irish versification whose names range from M to Z. It noted that Dr. P. Moloney, now of Collins Street, Melbourne, had produced some excellent and tender poetry (The Advocate, 1893).

Dr and Mrs. P Moloney attended the opening ceremony of the St. Vincent's Hospital. It was recalled that many doubts were expressed by many well-meaning people four years ago as to the expediency of the hospital (Advocate, 1893c).

Dr. P. Moloney opened the Fair and Village Festival at St Peter and Paul's new hall, South Melbourne, in the presence of a large number of persons (Advocate, 1894c).

Dr. P. Moloney was on a committee with many other leading citizens assisting the Count and Countess of Hopetoun planning the St. Vincent's Hospital Ball (Melbourne Punch, 1894).

The Archbishop of Melbourne, Dr. Carr, delivered an interesting and instructive lecture about art in Ancient Ireland at St. Patrick's College. Dr. P. Moloney seconded the vote of thanks in a speech laudatory of the Irish people in which he felt assured that the Irish people would again vindicate their claim to pre-eminence as an artistic and intellectual race (The Age, 1894; The Advocate, 1894).

Dr and Mrs. P Moloney and the Governor plus all the titled gentry and wives and the eminent citizens of Melbourne attended the St. Vincent's Hospital annual ball (Advocate, 1894b).

A lecture was delivered Rev. Dr. Carr on the subject of the "Great Cathedrals of the World," before the distinguished citizens of Melbourne. Sir John Madden proposed a vote of thanks to his Grace for the highly entertaining lecture and Dr Moloney proposed a vote of thanks to Madden for organising the event (Advocate, 1894).

St. Vincent's Hospital was reported to be in full working order in the charge of the devoted Sisters of Charity. The paper considered that patients would have the advantages of the talents and ability of leading members of the medical profession in Australia including Dr P. Moloney and other members of the honorary medical staff (Advocate, 1894).

Moloney attended the Melbourne Hospital fund raising ball (Weekly Times, 1894b).

Eileen Moloney, the gifted daughter of Dr. P. Moloney had completed her education at the Sacre Coeur Convent and was expected to leave Melbourne next year on a visit to Europe (Table Talk, 1894).

Molony gave a critique of the local production of 'The Merry Wives of Windsor to The Melbourne Shakespeare Society. He considered that the comedy was to be regarded as a kind of travesty in which Shakespeare had burlesqued both his own characters and those of other dramatists (Table Talk, 1895).

Dr P. Moloney had a deep interest in meteorology. When there was a shower of red coloured rain, a sulphur storm, he collected some of the red substance for microscopic and chemical examination (The Kyneton Observer, 1896).

Moloney attended the third annual meeting of the St Vincent's Hospital where he and the other honorary staff were thanked for their attendance, gratitude acknowledged by Moloney (The Argus, 1897a).

Moloney, a hirsute gentleman, suggested bushmen could reduce the risk of dysentery by filtering water from a dirty pool through their beard (The Herald, 1897)!

Moloney was one of many to attend St. Vincent's Hospital annual fund-raising ball (The Australasian, 1897).

Many doctors and other citizens contributed to the street illuminations of Melbourne.

Dr. Moloney provided a star in fairy lamps outside the Office of the "Argus" and the "Australasian" in white incandescent electric lamps and a crystal crown with the words "God Save the Queen" in electric lamps across the upper part of the building (The Age, 1897).

Moloney defended his beard in an amusing historical account of beards while listing his perception of their advantages. (Table Talk, 1897d).

Moloney and many doctors attended the funeral of Dr. Richard Youl who had been coroner for the city for some forty years and often performed inquests with Moloney. Aged seventy he had been for a considerable time past in failing health, but death from bronchitis came upon him suddenly. Born in Tasmania he was educated in England from an early age, then qualified M.R.C.S. 1842, M.D. (St Andrews) 1844. He studied in Paris for six months, gained experience in Edinburgh and London before migrating to Melbourne. His wife and two of his eleven children predeceased him (Leader, 1897a; The Age, 1897b; Australian Dictionary of Biography, n.d.).

Mrs. P. Moloney for once appeared in the press in preference to her husband for wearing a cream surah, costume, softly relieved 'with pearl passementerie and embroidered chiffon' to a ball (Table Talk, 1897a).

Moloney's brother, Jim Moloney, was elected alderman of Carlton South. He was also an excellent and witty after-dinner speaker and well-read also with occasional lapses into verse (Melbourne Punch, 1897b).

Moloney and his wife were among the distinguished guests invited to a reception held by the Roman Cathode Archbishop of Melbourne, Dr. Thomas Carr in honour of Cardinal Moran and visiting bishops (The Australian, 1897).

Dr and Mrs. Moloney attended a fancy-dress ball held by His Excellency the Governor and Lady Brassey at the Government House in which she appeared as Madame de Bontemps, in grey brocade, fichu, and powdered hair with pink roses, while Dr. P. Moloney appeared again in an unimaginative doctor's academic gown (Leader, 1897).

Moloney with his wife and daughter, Miss Eileen Moloney decided to leave Melbourne for an extended visit to Europe and were not expected to return until after the Paris Exhibition. Their Collins Street residence, including a well-selected library, were disposed of by auction (Table Talk, 1897b).

A reception was held by the Mayor of Melbourne for a Mr. Wilson Barrett, then a well-known English actor and playwright. Moloney gave a speech welcoming a Mr. J. C. Williamson, an American actor who was also present. 'Table Talk' noted that Moloney had long enjoyed the reputation of a graceful and effective speaker, but on this occasion his address reached a very high level of style, matter and delivery (The Argus, 1897b; Table Talk, 1897b).

The sale of Moloney's library attracted attention to his annotations in blue pencil. He wrote about Marcus Clarke, author of 'For the term of his natural life' and Moloney's patient, in Lombroso's 'The Man of Genius.' Lombroso wrote '*Lesions of the head and brain are very frequent among men of genius.*'

Marcus Clarke, when a child, received a blow from a horse's hoof, which crushed his skull leaving a deep scar on his skull four inches long. As a child he had disease of the left humerus, and a deep cicatrix nearly its entire length marked the operation for the removal of the dead bone. Marcus Clarke's left shoulder joint was ankylosed, and his left arm at least two inches shorter than the right. Hence, he wore a coat with his left hand pocketed (Table Talk, 1898).

In 1899 Moloney was residing in London, but Australia was not forgotten. He wrote a letter to a Melbourne friend saying that the strangest thing he has seen in London "is the extraordinary number of replicas of Melbourne men I meet every way I turn" (The Australasian, 1899).

Miss Eileen Moloney, Patrick Moloney's only daughter, a vivacious young Australian with the dark hair and creamy complexion characteristic of Celtic beauty, became engaged and later married to Mr. John Pius Poland, M.P., for South Kerry and barrister-at-law.

The bride was given away by her father and wore a gown of white peau-de-cygne and Brussels lace, made in Princess fashion, coronet of orange blossom, and tulle veil, her only ornament being a diamond necklace, presented by the bridegroom.

A reception was held at the present residence of Dr. and Mrs. Moloney, Queen Anne's Mansions, St. James's Park, and in the afternoon Mr. and Mrs. Poland left for Paris and Florence.

Moloney was described as a distinguished physician, whose name is known throughout.

Australia, where he is also known to be one of the finest living Shakespearian scholars. Not long ago Dr. Moloney spent a day at Stratford-on-Avon seeking out the various flowers mentioned in the works of Shakespeare (The Australasian, 1902a; Table Talk, 1902; Mount Alexander Mail, 1902).

Moloney's latest letter to his brother stated that Germany was the most sober place he had struck even though there was all night opening (Geelong Advertiser, 1902).

Family

Patrick Moloney married Ellen Quirk on 11 May 1876 at St Patrick's Cathedral, Melbourne, They had one daughter, Eileen, a gifted student. However, once graduated from school, the Victorian press commented regularly on her beauty and her gorgeous attire at social events rather than her intellect. The Advocate did report that she was great enthusiast in the movement for reviving the Gaelic tongue and has lately written a booklet on the subject (Advocate, 1902).

She married John Boland, who graduated with BAs from London and Oxford Universities and an MA from Oxford, won Tennis Olympic Gold medals and was M.P. for Kerry. They had one son and five daughters including Honor Boland, a Fianna Fail member of the Irish Parliament,

and Bridget Boland, the distinguished playwright and novelist.

Moloney would have taken great delight in the Irish republican and literary activities of his two granddaughters!

Conclusion

Patrick Moloney was a most knowledgeable competent doctor. Moloney was also a most sociable person. He participated in many societies outside his medical career. His speeches were much in demand and renowned for being well prepared, humorous, and relevant, but also most erudite with many appropriate literary references. He wrote songs and poetry; he was well versed in Latin and Greek reading the original versions of ancient Greek literature. He also blessed his audiences with his opinion on a wide variety of other topics including tea, stocking colours, cycling and swimming. One wonders how he fitted in his patients!

A native-born Irishman, he had kissed the Blarney Stone!

References

- Advocate*. (1879, May 24).
- Advocate*. (1881, December 3).
- Advocate*. (1883, December 29).
- Advocate*. (1884, June 14).
- Advocate*. (1886, January 9).
- Advocate*. (1887, August 20).
- Advocate*. (1887, October 8).
- Advocate*. (1888, July 7).
- Advocate*. (1889, August 17).
- Advocate*. (1890, December 4).
- Advocate*. (1891, November 14).
- Advocate*. (1891a, June 27).
- Advocate*. (1891b, May 2).
- Advocate*. (1892, December 3).
- Advocate*. (1893a, April 22).
- Advocate*. (1893b, March 25).
- Advocate*. (1893c, November 11).
- Advocate*. (1894a, August 25).
- Advocate*. (1894b, July 28).
- Advocate*. (1894c, March 31).
- Advocate*. (1894d, November 8).
- Advocate*. (1896, December 21).
- Advocate*. (1897, November 13).
- Advocate*. (1902, September 20).
- Age*. (1878, December 17).
- Australian Dictionary of Biography*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://adb.anu.edu.au>
- Ballarat Star*. (1881, July 26).
- Bendigo Advertiser*. (1885, June 2).
- Bendigo Advertiser*. (1885, June 6).
- Cobram Courier*. (1896, September 3).
- Geelong Advertiser*. (1872, July 10).
- Geelong Advertiser*. (1902, December 25).
- Herald*. (1883, May 1).
- Herald*. (1889, February 2).
- Illustrated Australian News*. (1882, January 27).
- Leader*. (1874, August 15).
- Leader*. (1887, April 23).
- Leader*. (1887, March 26).
- Leader*. (1892, March 12).
- Leader*. (1897a, August 14).
- Leader*. (1897b, November 6).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1877, August 16).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1882, December 14).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1883, March 15).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1884a, August 14).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1884b, August 21).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1884c, June 5).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1886, June 20).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1888a, July 26).

- Melbourne Punch*. (1888b, September 6).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1889a, January 24).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1889b, November 14).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1889c, November 21).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1889d, October 31).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1891, December 17).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1892, November 17).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1893, June 15).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1894, May 17).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1897a, January 14).
- Melbourne Punch*. (1897b, October 21).
- Melbourne Review*. (1877, July 7).
- Mount Alexander Mail*. (1889, October 2).
- Mount Alexander Mail*. (1902, December 5).
- Ovens and Murray Advertiser*. (1879, January 18).
- Punch*. (1887, November 17).
- Sportsman*. (1885, September 9).
- Sportsman*. (1889, November 27).
- Table Talk*. (1898, April 8).
- Table Talk*. (1885a, October 30).
- Table Talk*. (1885b, October 9).
- Table Talk*. (1889a, December 13).
- Table Talk*. (1889b, June 7).
- Table Talk*. (1889c, November 15).
- Table Talk*. (1889d, October 18).
- Table Talk*. (1890, October 31).
- Table Talk*. (1894, December 28).
- Table Talk*. (1894, December 28).
- Table Talk*. (1895, February 15).
- Table Talk*. (1897a, August 20).
- Table Talk*. (1897b, December 12).
- Table Talk*. (1897c, December 3).
- Table Talk*. (1897d, July 23).
- Table Talk*. (1898, April 23).
- Table Talk*. (1902, December 4).
- The Advocate*. (1879, June 7).
- The Advocate*. (1882, November 25).
- The Advocate*. (1891, March 28).
- The Advocate*. (1893, September 30).
- The Advocate*. (1894, June 30).
- The Age*. (1870, October 28).
- The Age*. (1872a, July 1).
- The Age*. (1872b, July 2).
- The Age*. (1873, September 2).
- The Age*. (1874, December 8).
- The Age*. (1875, March 19).
- The Age*. (1877, November 5).
- The Age*. (1878a, November 27).
- The Age*. (1878b, November 27).
- The Age*. (1879a, April 21).
- The Age*. (1879b, May 6).
- The Age*. (1880a, April 24).
- The Age*. (1880b, June 1).
- The Age*. (1880c, March 21).
- The Age*. (1881, December 13).
- The Age*. (1885a, August 21).
- The Age*. (1885b, December 23).
- The Age*. (1885c, October 30).
- The Age*. (1887, May 28).
- The Age*. (1890a, April 1).
- The Age*. (1890b, March 21).
- The Age*. (1890c, May 9).
- The Age*. (1892, March 25).
- The Age*. (1894a, February 14).
- The Age*. (1894a, June 23).
- The Age*. (1894a, September 29).

- The Age*. (1894b, June 23).
- The Age*. (1894c, September 29).
- The Age*. (1897a, August 9).
- The Age*. (1897a, June 22).
- The Age*. (1897b, August 9).
- The Age*. (1897b, June 22).
- The Argus*. (1872a, March 19).
- The Argus*. (1874a, December 1).
- The Argus*. (1874b, October 2).
- The Argus*. (1877, March 8).
- The Argus*. (1878, December 11).
- The Argus*. (1878c, November 30).
- The Argus*. (1879a, February 7).
- The Argus*. (1879b, February 8).
- The Argus*. (1879c, January 30).
- The Argus*. (1879d, February 4).
- The Argus*. (1879e, May 21).
- The Argus*. (1879f, May 29).
- The Argus*. (1879g, July 15).
- The Argus*. (1880a, April 10).
- The Argus*. (1880b, April 9).
- The Argus*. (1880c, July 5).
- The Argus*. (1880d, March 12).
- The Argus*. (1880d, September 25).
- The Argus*. (1882a, August 1).
- The Argus*. (1882a, August 1).
- The Argus*. (1882b, December 1).
- The Argus*. (1884, December 9).
- The Argus*. (1884a, December 9).
- The Argus*. (1885a, July 25).
- The Argus*. (1885a, May 26).
- The Argus*. (1885b, May 30).
- The Argus*. (1886, May 5).
- The Argus*. (1886a, May 5).
- The Argus*. (1887, June 4).
- The Argus*. (1887a, March 14).
- The Argus*. (1887b, September 13).
- The Argus*. (1887c, October 18).
- The Argus*. (1888a, February 3).
- The Argus*. (1888b, March 26).
- The Argus*. (1889, December 5).
- The Argus*. (1889a, December 5).
- The Argus*. (1891a, May 26).
- The Argus*. (1891b, June 26).
- The Argus*. (1892a, November 29).
- The Argus*. (1893a, April 27).
- The Argus*. (1897, December 8).
- The Argus*. (1897a, March 2).
- The Argus*. (1897b, December 8).
- The Australasian Sketcher with Pen and Pencil*. (1879, May 10).
- The Australasian Sketcher with Pen and Pencil*. (1882, January 14).
- The Australasian*. (1872, October 5).
- The Australasian*. (1878, December 23).
- The Australasian*. (1881, December 31).
- The Australasian*. (1884, June 7).
- The Australasian*. (1885a, June 20).
- The Australasian*. (1885b, November 1).
- The Australasian*. (1888, July 28).
- The Australasian*. (1892a, June 20).
- The Australasian*. (1892b, September 10).
- The Australasian*. (1897, June 12).
- The Australasian*. (1899, March 8).
- The Australasian*. (1899, March 8).
- The Australasian*. (1902a, August 23).
- The Australasian*. (1902b, June 21).
- The Australian*. (1897, November 6).
- The Ballarat Star*. (1887, July 12).

- The Herald.* (1871a, April 5).
The Herald. (1871b, October 21).
The Herald. (1877, December 17).
The Herald. (1879a, August 15).
The Herald. (1879b, May 29).
The Herald. (1881a, January 1).
The Herald. (1881b, June 15).
The Herald. (1886, March 11).
The Herald. (1887a, April 1).
The Herald. (1887b, March 22).
The Herald. (1888a, December 27).
The Herald. (1888b, December 7).
The Herald. (1888c, July 31).
The Herald. (1888d, September 19).
The Herald. (1889a, July 8).
The Herald. (1889b, March 12).
The Herald. (1889c, March 1).
The Herald. (1889d, September 26).
The Herald. (1890, February 11).
The Herald. (1891, April 18).
The Herald. (1892a, December 3).
The Herald. (1892b, March 12).
The Herald. (1894a, February 17).
The Herald. (1894b, November 2).
The Herald. (1897, May 10).
The Kyneton Observer. (1896, December 29).
The Riverina Herald. (1871, October 28).
The Riverina Herald. (1879, May 20).
Weekly Times. (1890, April 26).
Weekly Times. (1894a, November 1).
Weekly Times. (1894b, October 27).